

Security and Information

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With the argument that society needs to have certain products and / or services, the constituted powers create public bodies that are properly structured to act in a certain line of activity, such as education, security, health, social welfare, etc. In this way, they provide products and / or services directly to the population, who pay for them by collecting taxes.

With the emergence of mixed economy companies providing computer services it is no different from other public bodies, as they are entities created out of the interests of the members of a Government and aim, in principle, at the conception of a business model that encourages the scientific and technological development within the scope of Public Administration.

Due to their legal nature, they must necessarily seek organizational performance, translated into rates of return on investments made. To do this, they must sell products and / or services directly to public bodies and entities, which can use them in their strategic, tactical and operational activities. With this, directly or indirectly, the population will also be paying and benefiting from them, since they will be able to use them via public agencies.

Society demands from governments more and more smoothness and ethics in the treatment of public resources. When the Government chooses a group of managers to lead the direction of a mixed economy company providing computer services for a given term, the strategic decisions of those managers become important for all members of the organization, shareholders and mainly for society. Thus, it is hoped that the decisions made can contribute to the achievement of the organization's financial health, customer satisfaction and social well-being.

Conceptual

Information is written (recorded) knowledge in written (printed or numerical), oral or audiovisual form. Information has an element of meaning. It is a meaning transmitted to a conscious being by means of a message inscribed on a space-time medium: printed matter, electrical signal, sound wave, etc.

Organization

An organization can be any group of people, organized formally or informally. For example: an association of companies, a union, a federation, a political party, a residential condominium, residents of a neighbourhood, shopkeepers on a street or shopping centre, parents of students in a class, etc. An organization is an artificially created and structured social unit, continually altered to maintain itself over time, and with the function of reaching specific goals, which seek to satisfy the needs of its participants and society.

Information Technology

It can be any and all devices that have the capacity to process data and or information, both systemically and sporadically, whether applied to the product or applied in the process.

Information management

The term means the planning, construction, organization, management, training and control associated with information of any kind. The term can apply to both information itself and related resources, such as people, equipment, financial resources and technology.

Information

The definition of information is presented in various ways in the consulted literature. Information can be defined as "a fact, an event, a statement." However, if a fact is not communicated, it will not be information, as well as a statement, without the in fact, it will not be consistent. Thus, a more refined definition for information would be: a communicated fact.

Information is a process of transmission and transfer of knowledge: forms, data, and concepts, studies with the aim of making it accessible to another person, institution or society. The quality of this process will determine whether or not the individual's behaviour and attitude change receives the information. It is worth remembering that information is not synonymous with knowledge.

The term information has the following attributes: - considered almost as a synonym for the term fact;

- A reinforcement of what is already known;
- Freedom of choice when selecting a message;

- The raw material from which knowledge is extracted; what is exchanged with the outside world and not just received passively; defined in terms of its effects on the recipient; something that reduces uncertainty in a given situation.

Authors explain that information and knowledge are correlated but are not synonymous. It is also necessary to distinguish two types of knowledge:

- Codified knowledge - which, transformed into information, can be reproduced, plastered, transferred, acquired, traded, etc.

- Tacit knowledge.

Ideal characteristics of information

The information needs to be:

a) Clear: present the fact clearly, not masking it among the subsidiary facts.

b) Precise: must have a high standard of precision and never present terms such as: "around ...", "about ...", "more or less ...".

c) Quick: arrive at the decision point in a timely manner so that it can have an effect on that decision. Information can be clear and accurate, but arrive late, losing its "raison d'être".

d) Targeted: whoever needs it and who will decide based on that information.

It is important to note that the number of vehicles (means) of information fundamentally influences the quality of the information. Quality tends to decrease as the number of information vehicles increases.

Use of Information

There are three types of fundamental uses of information:

a) Information as a process: what a person knows changes when the subject is informed. In this sense, information is the action of informing, communicating knowledge or news of some fact or occurrence; the action of reporting the fact or occurrence; the action of deducing the fact, of having heard about something.

b) Information as knowledge: the concept of information is also used to assign the information product as a process. The communicated knowledge that relates to a particular fact, subject or event; what one captures or what one says; intelligence, news.

The notion of information as one that reduces uncertainty can be seen as a particular case of information as knowledge. On some occasions, information increases uncertainty.

Information as a thing: the concept of information is also used for objects, such as data or documents, which are referred to as information because they are considered as "informational", as having the quality of correcting knowledge or communicating information.

Information management

Information is considered a factor in business strategy, the professional is trained to work with administrative problems related to information in the areas of collection, identification, treatment, organization, distribution and use in the administrative and productive process.

Another option is the area of marketing and sales, including the search for new products required by the market. The technician is prepared to be always updated and attentive to the constant changes in the world of information, in new programming languages and operational environments.

Of course, it also requires knowledge of information technology both with regard to hardware and software.

Information is a strategic resource that has cost, price and value. As such it must be managed in the same way as the financial, material and human resources within your organization are managed.

The growing need to manage information, considering the related human and information technology aspects resulted in the proposal to form a professional area, originally called «Information Resources Management».

Translated as «Information Management», it is configured as a study area already considered in Europe, whose theoretical and operational contents have become an essential tool for any organization that needs to produce, locate, collect, test , store, distribute and encourage the use of information.

The interdisciplinary relationship between Information Management and Information Science, administration and information technology results in a set of qualifications and theoretical and practical knowledge that enable the structuring of information systems, as well as the provision of information services, products and activities.

An increasing number of small, medium and large institutions, of a private or governmental nature, which start to organize themselves in the dynamics of the global

transformations of the «Information Society», are obliged to adopt information management programs, aiming at the ethical performance of its activities and an adequate decision-making process.

Science of Information

Science of Information is the discipline that investigates the properties and behaviour of information, the forces that govern its flow and the means of processing information for maximum accessibility and utility. It has a pure science component that researches the subject unrelated to its application and an applied science component that develops services and products (H. Borko, synthesizing ideas exposed by Robert S. Taylor).

Administration

Information Management (IM) helps to increase business competitiveness and organizational modernization processes from the point of view of planning and strategic use of information and associated technologies, as well as quality specifications, content and information security in the company.

Computing

The relationship between GI and Informatics lies in its application in the storage and retrieval of information and its dissemination in databases and computer networks suitable for different information systems.

Information society

Human community that, due to technological changes, started to have its survival and development actions based on the creation, storage, distribution and intensive use of information resources.

Information systems

Any system that uses or does not use Information Technology resources, manipulates and generates information can generally be considered an Information System.

Information technology

The term «Information Technology» is any activity that involves information processing and integrated communication through electronic equipment.

This term is more comprehensive and refers to all types of technology that operate with information, whether in an information system, in the automation of an industrial process, in the communication between computers of two organizations, or even in the personal use of computational resources.

For Burgelman (1996, p. 91), Information Technology «refers largely to the resources applied by a firm in the processing and management of its data. These resources include hardware, software, communications (voice, data, and video) and associated personnel. »

Information Technology is defined as the capabilities offered by computers, applications - software - and telecommunications. IT is technologies and applications that combine the processing and storage of data with the ability to transmit remotely from telecommunications.

Based on the definitions of the aforementioned authors, it appears that IT has as basic components the processing of data and / or information and the integrated communication through electronic equipment for this.

Information Technology and its Impacts

Technology is conceptualized as the set of knowledge, special and mainly scientific, that apply to a certain branch of activity; it can also be considered as a science that deals with technique in a more comprehensive and systematic way.

Technology is a package of organized information, of different types (scientific, empirical ...), coming from various sources (scientific discoveries, patents, books, manuals, drawings...), obtained by different methods (research, development, copying, espionage ...) and used in the production of goods and services.

The knowledge and skills used in the production of these technological packages constitute technological training.

It is not bought, but it is built over time, the result of an evolutionary process. It is an attribute, a competence that needs to be developed and improved based on the recognition that the organization is, above all, a training organization.

The growing evolution and integration of the elements that make up IT (hardware, software, communication networks, workstation [CAD, CAM, CIM, etc.], robotics and smart chips) have revolutionized the way of living, communicating, thinking and doing business. As information technology is incorporated into the production system, it radically changes the structure and the way in which work is performed, especially with regard to production and coordination work.

Types of Information Technology

To obtain reference on the possibilities of strategic use of IT, it is necessary to know the set that comprises it. The following can be considered as IT

Categories:

- a) Hardware technology;
- b) Information systems;
- c) Office automation;
- d) Computer engineering and design;
- e) Industrial automation;
- f) Specific automation resources;
- g) Multimedia resources.

This systematization of the most relevant set of Information Technology serves as a brief guide for researching the main strategic uses and must be constantly updated, as any classification regarding Information Technology becomes obsolete quickly, due to the speed of advances in this area .

Typology and examples of IT:

- a) Technologies related to information technology planning - information technology methodologies; modeling of data and processes; methodologies for preparing the Informatics Master Plan;
- b) Technologies related to systems development - systems development methodologies; project management methodologies; program testing and debugging methodologies; systems analysis techniques; systems design techniques; prototype techniques; database design techniques; programming techniques;
- c) Technologies related to software support - operating systems; database management systems; teleprocessing software; utilities; performance monitors; programming language; application generators;
- d) Technologies related to production processes and operations - PCP; capacity planning; performance management;

e) Technologies related to hardware support - supercomputers; large computers; computer network; local networks; micro-mainframe connection; microcomputers; RISC architecture; graphic stations.

Having knowledge of the various types of existing IT, the next step is to understand how they can be used in organizations to support organizational strategies.

The Use of Information Technology in Organizations

Nowadays, the rapid changes that occur in the business environment require organizations to adapt and seek new ways to compete and differentiate themselves from the competition.

One of the forces that is causing the greatest changes is Information Technology, which is also the core of many of the innovations used by organizations to succeed or even survive.

Information technology is now used as a tool to promote competitiveness and acquire and / or sustain a competitive advantage over its competitors.

This growing strategic use of IT occurs due to a change in the conception of the role of information in organizations.

Until the 1960s, information was often associated with the tasks of designing, producing and distributing a product and / or service. The decentralization of companies after the Second World War increased the need for centralized financial control. In the 1950s, information systems were created whose main objective was to reduce costs and time in paper processing, especially in the accounting area.

The first information system created was a semi-automatic system, called Electronic Accounting Machines (EAM), which served to increase the speed of the accounting area. This system simply automated an existing procedure (LAUDON; LAUDON, 1996).

In the 1960s, the organization came to recognize that information could be used to support management in general. For these authors, the emergence of the mainframe allowed companies to process data centrally, with the mainframe becoming the centre of the company's IT operations.

Management Information Systems were developed, whose main proposal was to increase the speed of the required reports.

At that time, IT applications focused on the automation of repetitive tasks and IT investment decisions, in general, were evaluated in terms of reducing labour costs.

Laudon and Laudon (1996) also comment that in the 1970s and early 1980s, Information Technology started to be conceived for a standardized management control of the entire organization.

Decision Support Systems and Executive Support Systems emerged that improved and increased the speed of the decision-making process of specific managers and executives in a wide range of problems.

According to those authors, even in the 1970s, the introduction of minicomputers allowed firms to develop applications to serve specific departments or groups to supplement the centralized functions that functioned on the mainframe.

The data on these two different platforms could be processed independently or shared across networks. The minicomputer also boosted the use of IT in firms that lacked the financial capacity to invest in the mainframe.

At that time, the return on investment in Information Technology was related to cost reduction. Computers and communication equipment and the personnel involved were brought together in a data processing centre.

Users accessed data online by consulting a computer terminal or through reports. The data centre was also responsible for the development of various software that processed and updated the data for users.

The Management Information System department was also common. This department had a team of analysts and programmers who identified, designed and developed new software to support the firm's activities.

Computer resources were considered instruments to support business (TURBAN, 1996). In the mid-1980s, the conception of information became that of a strategic resource, a potential source of competitive advantage and a strategic weapon. Strategic systems appeared to guarantee the organization's survival and prosperity.

Strategic information systems could be used at all levels of the organization and their scope was broader and deeper than the other types of systems described.

Information Technology then assumed a more integrating role, in which business execution depended more and more on its application. The introduction of the personal computer (PC) and a proliferation of hardware and software standards have brought about a change in organizations and the role played by IT.

As the PCs had a lower cost than the mainframe, managers started to develop individual applications outside the control of the MIS department, causing a decentralization of information. These applications met departmental needs (LAUDON; LAUDON, 1996).

Information technology has come to involve all the company's main divisions, dozens of full-time programmers, external consultants and multiple machines (or remote computers connected by telecommunications networks), and perhaps hundreds of end users in the organization who used the same data for diverse applications.

Data, instead of being located and controlled by the data processing center, became usable by hundreds of employees from their computers, each more powerful than the big computers of the mid 1980s. This system introduces changes management and institutional.

In the view of Laudon and Laudon (1996), this new hardware makes the software more powerful, easier to use for beginners. Within hours, relatively unskilled employees can learn to use a word processor and prepare schematics and telecommunications applications on a microcomputer.

In addition, it is now possible for end users to design their own simple applications and systems without the help of programmers.

In the early 1990s, IT enabled business transformation, acquiring a strategic character. The evolution of the role of this technology is linked to scientific and technological advances in the IT area, to the pressures of an increasingly competitive environment and to changes in the design of business management strategies.

There is a growing interdependence between business strategies, roles and procedures, on the one hand, and software, hardware, data and telecommunications, on the other.

A change in any of these components often requires changes in other components.

The technological advancement of microcomputers, the progress of communications that carry data, voices, sounds and images, the application of information technology and telecommunications to improve products, services and organizations allow the profile of the information society to be characterized more and more clearly (LAUDON ; LAUDON, 1996). Torre (1995) emphasizes that we are experiencing an evolution from the domain through natural resources to the domain through strategic resources, among which are the knowledge and information.

Laudon and Laudon (1996) argue that, in this context, Information Technology plays an important role, as it democratizes information and makes it available to practically everyone.

Today, Information Technology helps to create and disseminate knowledge and information throughout the organization through new knowledge work systems, applications, providing access to company-wide data and communication networks.

IT is now seen as a fundamental tool to trigger business and its use becomes one of the biggest factors responsible for the success of organizations, whether in terms of survival, or in achieving greater competitiveness.

The author also states that, due to this, the dependence of organizations in relation to IT becomes increasingly greater. In view of its growing importance, as well as its relevant role in obtaining the organization's competitiveness, the planning of its use must be part of the organizational strategies.

The organization's IT use strategy must be consistent with its business strategy. It is this alignment that must guarantee the allocation of resources for IT projects and provide guidelines for their planning and priorities.

The main factors that contribute to the misalignment between business and IT strategies:

- Pressure from suppliers of business technology solutions
- IT management model still very much tied to traditional information models: centralized;
- Profile of IT management professionals
- IT professionals with an overly technical view;
- IT vision as a final activity, instead of a means;
- Not considering IT in the strategic context;
- Divergence in the training of Chief Information Officer (CIO) and Chief Executive Officer (CEO)
- Distribution of computing to the end user;
- Broken promises;
- Disputes over space and power;
- Poorly defined IT structure;
- internal conflicts of the organization;
- lack of distribution of responsibilities regarding the success / failure in the development of IT solutions;
- low participation of CEOs in the IT area;
- lack of harmony between the IT management of the corporation and the IT management of its business areas;

- Communication problems regarding language;
- Reduction of the IT group;
- Low commitment by the high leadership to the success / failure of planned IT solutions;
- Positioning of the CEO regarding the potential of IT;
- Lack of capacity for IT professionals to prioritize projects;
- Low ability to understand strategies;
- Problems in the strategy communication process
- High turnover in the position of CEO.

The challenge for executives in organizations and IT executives is the search for convergence between IT and business strategies (HENDERSON, 1989).

The alignment of IT strategies to business strategies seeks to highlight the potential of IT, considering it as an indispensable resource during the strategy definition process, as well as other variables such as product / service positioning, manufacturing strategies, distribution strategies.

To enable such alignment, it is essential that those responsible for formulating business strategies and top management are aware of the possibilities of using IT and that they are well advised on the opportunities that they can generate.

On the other hand, those responsible for formulating strategies for using Information Technology and its management must have a good knowledge of the organization's business.

The identification of the use of Information Technology as a support for organizational strategies can occur, and often occurs, through an almost intuitive process. However, it is necessary to systematize this entire process.

The risk of using IT without planning is mentioned by McGaughey, Snyder and Carr (1994), who affirm that the increasing use of IT, while enhancing the capacity of organizations to obtain, maintain or combat competitive advantages, also increases the management risks, inherent in any type of decision.

To facilitate the process of using IT as a strategic resource, some bases must be explored: the optimal product and process concepts; the application of the systemic view and the essential view in the analysis of problems / systems and in the search for innovative solutions; which Information Technology can be used to make the company

more competitive; which fundamental aspects of business strategy can assist in systematizing the search for solutions with strategic impact.

Considering these issues, managers may be better able to assess whether their companies are ready to use IT to support organizational strategies.

The definition of opportunities and competitive advantages with the use of Information Technology must follow the following steps:

- Understanding the concepts of competitive forces and strategies;
- Definition of critical competitive forces for the company;
- Definition of the strategies that the company adopts;
- Assessment of the impact of Information Technology;
- Definition of the company's degree of dependence in relation to Information Technology;
- Definition of opportunities for strategic application of Information Technology.

Another important point to be considered in the introduction of Information Technology in organizations is related to the support of senior staff in this process. There is a direct relationship between the level of success of an IT strategy and the level of support from top management, due to its influence on the other participants and its role as sponsor of the project.

As long as all the steps for using Information Technology as a strategic resource are observed, it can make the organization more competitive in its market, changing the current performance standard:

- a) It causes changes in the organization of the work process (work becomes more abstract, reduction of time and space, continuous availability of knowledge, new forms of business management);
- b) It enables the integration between the various business units at the level of the organization and beyond its borders (virtual production chain). The competitiveness of companies depends on a good interaction with suppliers and customers, which can also be achieved via IT;
- c) Changes the competitive nature of many industries (strategic alliances and cooperative agreements between competitors, in which companies cooperate to share resources and services, gaining a competitive advantage);
- d) Provides new strategic opportunities for organizations, causing an assessment and redefinition of the mission, goals, strategies and operations;

e) Requires changes in management strategies and organizational structure, assuming a change in organizational culture.

The new winning company model has a tendency to decrease the number of hierarchical levels and greater delegation of powers. This trend can be enhanced with the use of Information Technology.

But, despite offering organizations the possibility of guaranteeing greater competitiveness, the competitive advantages conferred by Information Technology do not necessarily last long enough to ensure long-term profits. Innovations that were introduced as a strategic resource often become a tool for survival.

As the environment is constantly changing, it is necessary to plan business and IT strategies in relatively shorter times. In addition, it is necessary that the organization is sufficiently flexible, so that it can adapt to the new realities that it will face throughout the process.

Another important aspect to note is that the implementation of frequent technological innovations requires far-reaching socio-technical changes, which requires a relatively long period for adaptation. This goal is not easy to achieve because individuals resist change; both those that are imposed on an organization and those that employees are subjected to when their work is remodelled. This is one of the biggest obstacles to strategic transitions.

Conclusion

Therefore, for this process to be successful, it is necessary that those responsible for implementing Information Technology have a greater understanding of organizational change.

References

Bruce D. Henderson The Origin of Strategy- Harvard Business Review From the November–December 1989 Issue.

Magal, Simha R.; Houston H. Carr; and Hugh J. Watson. "Critical Success Factors for Information Center Managers," MIS Quarterly, Vol. 12, Nr. 3 (September 1988), 413-425. 5.

Watson, Hugh J. and Houston H. Carr. "Organizing for DSS Support: The End User Services Alternative," Journal of Management Information Systems, Vol. 4, No. 1 (Summer 1987), 83-95.

Carr, Houston H. "Factors That Affect User-Friendliness in Interactive Computer Programs," *Information & Management* 22:3 (March 1992), 137-149. 7.

Laudon, J. C. (1996). *Markets and Privacy*. Communications of the ACM

Loch, Karen D.; Houston H. Carr; and Merrill E. Warkentin. "Threats to Information System Security: Management's Perceptions Reflect Yesterday's Environment," *Management Information Systems Quarterly* 16:2 (June 1992), 173- 186. 8.

Magal, Simha R. and Houston H. Carr. "An Investigation of the Effects of Age, Size, and Hardware Options on the Critical Success Factors Applicable to Information Centers," *Journal of Management Information Systems*, Vol. 4, No. 4 (Spring 1988), 60-76. 9.

Charles A. Snyder; and Houston H. Carr. "Implementing Information Technology for Competitive Advantage: Risk Management Issues" *Information & Management*, 26 (1994), 273-80. 11.

Carr, Houston H. "Debate Continues Over Accountability for Internal Computer Use," *Data Management*, Vol. 25, No. 9 (September 1987), 16-17, 20-21. 14.

Gibson, Michael L.; Charles A. Snyder; and Houston H. Carr. "Implementing Corporate-wide Information Strategy Through CASE," *Journal of Information Systems Management*, 7:3 (Summer 1990), 8-17.

Houston H. Carr; and Simha R. Magal. "Trends in Information Centers," *Information Resources Management Journal* 5:3 (Summer 1992) pp. 5-14. 27.

Houston H. Carr; R. Kelly Rainer; and Simha R. Magal. "The Evolving Role of the Information Center", *Information Resources Management Journal* 5:3 (Summer 1992), 5-14. 28.